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Post-pandemic Resilient Communities: Is the Informal Economy a Reservoir for the Next Generation of Digitalized and Green Businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and Innovation: Building Post-pandemic Resilient Communities in Mexico.

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Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project with the aim of investigating the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

This Mexico-focused report draws on qualitative and desk-based methods, including literature review, policy and media analysis, and grey literature, to investigate emerging socio-economic and political-economic trends in the country's informal sector. Unlike other country reports that may rely on large-scale quantitative data or automated keyword mapping, this contribution offers an in-depth interpretive analysis grounded in ethnographic sensibilities and critical development scholarship.

Key findings suggest that while service-oriented and urban informal sectors (e.g. tourism, retail, transport) were deeply affected by the pandemic, small-scale agriculture remained relatively resilient. At the same time, grassroots innovations have emerged in digital inclusion and alternative economies, although infrastructural and socio-political barriers persist. This report emphasizes the importance of recognizing indigenous and community-based economic practices as legitimate responses to crisis, and calls for policy approaches that respect autonomy and cultural specificity.

Keywords

Mexican Economy; Macroeconomic Stability; Economic Growth; Privatization; Competitiveness; International Trade Liberalization; Global Value Chains; Economic Polarization; Political Disenchantment; Post-pandemic Recovery; Poverty; Emigration; Inequalities; Informal Economy; Extractivism; Organized Crime; Political and Social Uncertainties; Corruption; Violence; NAFTA.

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Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Mexican country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report builds on a qualitative, anthropologically informed approach, focusing on sectoral fluctuations and also on how local actors interpret, resist, or creatively adapt to structural pressures.

In this Mexican case, no large-scale statistical dataset or automated bibliometric analysis was used. Instead, the methodological approach focused on:

- A thematic review of literature, reports, and critical essays related to informality, livelihoods, and resilience in Mexico.
- Analysis of grey literature, policy documents, and national and international development discourse.
- A comparative reading of media narratives and regional reports, actively including sources coming from non-conventional and independent media, which are often more attuned to grassroots perspectives and less filtered by institutional agendas.
- Engagement with anthropological and critical development studies addressing indigenous and community-based economies.

This interpretive and grounded approach is consistent with PRESILIENT's epistemological stance, which doesn't reduce informality to a statistical anomaly to be corrected, recognizing it instead as a field of knowledge, agency, and innovation. As such, the report highlights the political and ethical dimensions of economic practices, where the informal economy is often tied to broader struggles for autonomy, dignity, global justice, and environmental sustainability. In this context, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of post-pandemic dynamics and will inform the subsequent phases of the project, including expert-based Delphi surveys and case study development. They also offer policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant assumptions about formalization and proposing alternative economic imaginaries rooted in lived experience.

Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the common research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also followed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. The data collection process was based

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on the identification and use of pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. In line with the shared methodological guidelines, the research drew on approximately 150 sources, comprising—where available—50 academic references, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents. These materials were selected through targeted searches, curated for relevance, and then closely read, coded, and interpreted in light of the researcher’s contextual knowledge and disciplinary perspective. Each step of this process—keyword selection, source collection, critical reading, and report drafting—is made explicit to reinforce methodological transparency. Although the emphasis in this Mexican case is on qualitative synthesis and ethnographic sensibility, the report remains anchored in a systematic data-gathering process shared across the PRESILIENT network. This contributes to a robust and comprehensive report that stands on its own, aligned with the project’s collective aims and epistemological commitments.

A further added value of this report lies in its comprehensive bibliography, which brings together a systematically selected corpus of 150 sources. This tri-fold dataset was curated through targeted keyword-based searches and thematic relevance screening, ensuring a diverse and robust representation of perspectives on informality in Mexico. This bibliographic collection supports the present analysis and serves as a valuable resource for future research on informal economies and resilience in the Mexican context and can act as a foundation for comparative studies or policy-oriented investigations.

Informal Economies in Mexico: Socioeconomic Context

In Mexico, the COVID-19 pandemic has emphasized both the resilience and vulnerability of informal economies, which in this country comprise a substantial part of the workforce. The most affected sectors include tourism, transportation, and retail, which were deeply impacted by mobility restrictions and reduced consumption. Informal workers in these sectors, already lacking job security and social protection, faced significant income loss that further exacerbated precarious working conditions. However, agriculture demonstrated some resilience, largely due to Mexico’s extensive network of small-scale farms that provided essential food security in the face of supply chain disruptions.

Regional and Global Comparison

When comparing Mexico with other countries in Latin America, a similar pattern emerges. Countries such as Ecuador and Brazil also saw agriculture as a relatively stable sector, while service-oriented and urban informal economies struggled. However, unlike some South American countries, Mexico’s proximity to the United States facilitated a relatively quicker recovery in specific sectors, accelerated by trade and remittances, which became a source of relief for many informal workers’ households.

Globally, Mexico shares commonalities with Southeast Asian countries like Vietnam and Thailand, where informal economies are widespread and substantial, and pandemic-induced shifts accelerated digital adoption. Yet, Mexico’s digital transition has been slower due to infrastructural

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gaps and limitations in the access to digital tools for informal workers. The urban-rural divide further complicates this accessibility, making digital solutions less feasible in rural communities reliant on traditional methods of exchange and subsistence farming. Comparatively, Kenya and Senegal demonstrated innovative approaches to digital finance, such as mobile money, whereas Mexico's informal sector has remained relatively underserved in this area.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

Post-pandemic, Mexico has seen a growing interest in integrating informal workers into digital economies, although challenges remain. Grassroots initiatives, similar to those in Kenya, have emerged, providing community-based digital finance and e-commerce platforms to support informal workers. Mexico's informal economy also aligns with global trends of increased job insecurity and inequality, further exacerbated by the pandemic.

Popular economic practices in Mexico's informal sector should not be simplistically viewed as obstacles but rather as expressions of resilience, adaptability, and community-oriented values that challenge capitalist norms of economic "formality". From an anthropological perspective, transitioning to formal structures presupposes standards rooted in Western-centric models of employment, income measurement, and productivity that may not fully respect or accommodate the cultural and social roles these informal practices evoke. Rather than enforcing formalization, which often brings increased regulation and loss of autonomy, recognizing and supporting these methods as viable and valuable forms of economic activity aligns with indigenous ontologies and communal frameworks. This shift in perspective allows us to question who defines economic trends and "success" and to acknowledge that informal economies serve local needs and uphold community values that formal (and neoliberal) markets often overlook.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Mexico). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the*

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pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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